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Family and Management-Related Factors as Correlates of the Elements of Change

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Abstract

The electorate selected local public officials based on their name recognition, family status, family ties, and ability to manage their constituents. Public officials should embody the elements of change of knowledge, attitude, and skill to serve their people better. This study the significant relationship between family-related and management-related factors with the elements of change in local public officials. It delves into family-related aspects, including family ties, family status, family responsibility, and parental authority; management-related factors were limited to policy formulation, policy implementation, decision-making, and leadership style. It utilized the Pearson correlations. The study discovered that the respondents' Family Ties, Family Status, and Family Responsibility were partially significantly related to the elements of change. Leadership Style is markedly correlated with all variables of elements of change. Politically, the respondents had an impression that they were doing well with their political obligations. Public officials are also political managers and cannot avoid their responsibilities. It is difficult for career general managers to underline the significance of their political platform due to electoral cycles and their brief tenure as stated by law.

Keywords: Attitude, Skill, Social Science, Public Administration, Public Officials, Family, Management Factors, Elements of Change, descriptive, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

Citizens elect local leaders. Choosing a leader depends on popularity, prominence, name recognition, philanthropy, economic standing, and other factors. Knowledge, attitude, and skill rarely determine a candidate's selection. The problem with these local public officials' leadership is not their popularity, status, or charity activity but their lack of knowledge in their chosen field, in some cases, on the development of the local community's food system (Emas and Jones, 2021). While attitude is crucial and shaped by performance perceptions adjusted for expectations (Seyd, 2015), they demonstrated skills that the business owners have manifested as well-appointed to dominate their constituents (Kirkland, 2021). Most public officials dislike authoring bills, letters, and meeting minutes. Public leaders considered attitude intrinsic. Filipinos are known for their seamless interpersonal relationships, hospitality, and charity. Likewise, public officials lack skill. The Skill involves using information and combining experiences. Suppose local public officials are compared to private individuals while seeking a job. In that case, criteria must be met, aside from gathering the appropriate paperwork, the long queue for submission, and the battery of paper-test and panel interviews to garner attractiveness and recruitment.

This way, local public officials should not be exempt from citizen selection. They must endure suffering and hardship to raise citizen consciousness, seek consideration, and gain votes. Most public servant candidates portray themselves as the solution to all problems or as knowing society's flaws. Human Resources may examine an applicant's profile in a private business to see if it meets job needs and skills. The management then questions and answers about knowledge, attitude, and skill. The management then questions and answers about knowledge, attitude, and skill. Citizens must choose local public leaders based on their ideals and levels of education to lead and control society.

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Public leaders are comparable to corporate managers because they are most effective when placed in positions where they should resolve problems (Spradlin, 2012). Plato once gave his conception of an ideal society, wherein they prepared the citizens as political leaders from their first year of age until becoming philosophers-king at the age of fifty. Plato's educational election prepares local politicians for public service their whole lives.

Framework

When a corporate leader sees that his organization needs fundamental change, one of the first and most crucial actions is to assemble a team to drive a change project. These individuals will be the change agents whose success will decide the organization's transformation effort and need to answer the question if they have the proper knowledge, attitude, and skills (Kaufmann & Tan, 2017). It is hypothesized in this study that factors of family and management have a significant level of relation over the elements of change. On the aspect of family ties, according to Salcedo et al. (2002), a study of family structures in India, China, and Japan reveals distinctive traits. This traditional family is prevalent in the rural areas of the Philippines, but aunts, uncles, nieces, and nephews may also cohabitate. In addition, according to Salcedo et al. (2009), the closeness of familial ties has weakened the individual's commitment to the government. The belief that the family is genuine and the government is impersonal has roots in Spanish rule. When there is a connection between the family and the workplace, irregularities such as nepotism emerge. It demonstrates that family and politics are intertwined and interdependent in an organization. Salcedo et al. (1999) noted that the success of one family member equals the success of the entire family; conversely, his mistakes and misdeeds reflect negatively on all family members; there is mutual financial and emotional dependency among family members. The stated literature emphasized the need to maintain a stable family structure. It demonstrated a trend toward extravagance and the acquisition of consumer goods rather than savings that generate income. Salcedo et al. (2002) parental authority noted that it is difficult to eradicate the deeply rooted authoritarian beliefs that children should only be seen and not heard. The father has the God-given right to rule, and the wife should be submissive to him as her lord and master. Salcedo et al. (1999) noted that the family provides some form of social security and insurance. It is evident and part of our customs that a child who has reached adulthood helps sustain their family, assist in their siblings' education, and care for their parents.

Busto (2003) asserts that the father and mother are both responsible for their children, who are not yet adults. If there is a disagreement, the father's decision will be the one that stands unless a court says otherwise. As long as they are under their parent's authority, children must obey them and show them respect and awe. On the management-related factors, policymaking and implementation entail both a technical and political process of formulating and coordinating the aims and means of stakeholders. Thus, policies are actions containing objectives and the methods to attain them, regardless of how well or poorly they are defined, justified, communicated, and formulated (Howlett and Cashore, 2014). On the former literature, this study will assess the significance of local public officials as policymakers based on their knowledge of the intricate interrelationships between their values and their policy development processes. It will also consider the concerns and ideas of the various public sectors or the general public regarding their role as influencers and persuaders in policymaking. Buchanan and O'Connell (2006) used Herbert Simon's argument that complicated situations, limited time, and a lack of mental processing power make it hard for people to make good decisions. The referenced literature has relevance to the current research. Every individual is tasked with making decisions every minute and every day, whether they are essential or highly complex. As administrators and policymakers, public officials have the weighty responsibility to make crucial decisions, especially on policy analysis. Pratiwi et al. (2020) found that a leader's style positively and significantly affects how well state officials do their jobs. It means that leaders need to know where their people are, how they are doing, and how the workplace is set up. The government's legitimacy as the regime is strengthened by how well the political leaders do their jobs. It makes it more likely that the administration will last. The political leadership also

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handles all national conflicts. Robust and effective leadership can organize groups and institutions toward an acceptable consensus, ensuring stability and keeping conflicts within manageable limits.

This paper looks at Kurt Lewin's Change Theory, a way of thinking about how things change. He devised a three-step change model: "unfreeze, change, and refreeze." In this model, learning from the past is thrown out and replaced with (Current Nursing, 2020). In this theory, there are driving forces that cause occurrences, while in this study, the family and management-related factors function as the driving and restraining forces. Another theory is the Classification of Learning Outcomes by Kraiger et al. on 1993, which focuses on cognitive, skill-based, and affective learning outcomes (Learning Outcome, 2021.). The mental, skill-based, and affective learning outcomes are the knowledge, attitude, and skill counterparts that identify the end states of training. This theory views learning outcomes as a change in verbal knowledge alone (Bright, 2021).

Fig. 1 Paradigm of the Study

This study focuses on elected local officials' family and management-related factors in Central Luzon. Using a model with independent and dependent variables also established its restrictions. The independent variables comprise family and management-related aspects, whereas the dependent variables consist of the elements of change. Family-related factors include family ties, family status, family responsibility, and parental authority; management-related factors include policy formulation, policy implementation, decision-making, and leadership style. In addition, the study investigated the functional relationship between the elements of change in knowledge, attitude, and skill.

Objectives of the Study

The study's primary purpose is to determine the family and management-related factors that affect the elements of change of the local public officials in Central Luzon. Specifically, the study sought to answer the question, are there significant relationships between family and management-related factors with the elements of change? It is hypothesized that there is no significant relationship between family and management-related factors with the elements of change of the local public officials.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study used the descriptive-inferential design, utilizing the procedure of Birion et al. (2005). It was conducted in San Jose Delmonte City, San Jose City, and the Municipality of San Felipe, involving a purposive sample of 98 respondents. The survey questionnaire used in this study consists of three (3) parts. Part I is family-related factors

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such as family ties, family status, family responsibilities, and parental authority. Part II contains the management-related factors on policy formulation, policy implementation, decision-making, and leadership style. Part III includes the elements of change in local public officials' knowledge, attitude, and skill. The final draft was submitted for a dry run to local public officials of Olongapo City. The dummy respondents were asked to comment on the items in the questionnaire if they found them exciting and significant in the study and for revision. A Cronbach's Alpha of 0.929 resulted in a reliability test and a validity test of a critical r value of 0.1986, which is less than the obtained total value for each item in the instrument. The researcher furnished a letter of endorsement to the Office of the City Mayor of San Jose Del Monte City, Municipal Mayor of San Felipe, and City Mayor of San Jose City upon acceptance and receiving confirmation it was coursed to the barangay captain/respondents. The researcher was responsible for furnishing the respondent's questionnaire with a few assistants who engender coordination among all barangay captains/respondents to facilitate dependable distribution and retrieval of the questionnaires. The study used the following statistical techniques: frequency, percentage, mean, and Pearson-product moment correlation coefficient.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Exploring the relationships between family and management-related factors with the elements of change. Pearson product-moment correlation was performed. Almost all family and management variables have a relationship with the elements of change.

Table 1. Mean Table for Family & Management-Related Factors with the Elements of Change

FAMILY-RELATED FACTORS		
	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Family Ties	4.42	Highly Performed
Family Status	4.01	Moderately Performed
Family Responsibility	4.42	Highly Performed
Parental Authority	4.45	Highly Performed
Average Mean	4.33	Highly Performed
MANAGEMENT-RELATED FACTORS		
	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Policy Formulation	4.41	Highly Performed
Policy Implementation	4.44	Highly Performed
Decision Making	4.11	Performed
Leadership	4.85	Highly Performed
Average Mean	4.45	Highly Performed
ELEMENTS OF CHANGE		
	Mean	Descriptive Rating
Knowledge	4.72	Highly Performed
Attitude	3.97	Performed
Skill	4.89	Highly Performed
Average Mean	4.53	Highly Performed

Family-related factors. A similar finding of high correlations (HC) is attributed to family ties with knowledge $r(98) = .622$, $p < .001$, and skill with $r(98) = .604$, $p < .001$. The family is like a political organization. Each member has a position to assume a standard set of norms and values. The parents dictate the norms and standards observed in the house. House rules on chores and work responsibility clearly define the behavior and etiquette to be manifested by each family member. Family status with attitude has high correlations (HC) that show an $r(98) = .685$, $p < .001$, which concerns beliefs and perspectives on rearing children, providing education, offering monetary help, prioritizing health needs, and the fact that the respondents are part of a political clan in their town shows how much they value their family. Family responsibility has high correlations (HC) in all aspect of element of change, in knowledge $r(98) = .672$, $p < .001$, attitude $r(98) = .620$, $p < .001$, and skill $r(98) = .603$, $p < .001$. The local public

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officials are highly oriented and focused on their responsibilities and functions as family members. However, they are also aware of their sense of responsibility to the public, which signifies both a sense of duty and an effective delineation of their essential roles within the family. Parental authority with knowledge $r(98) = .601, p < .001$, it is generally accepted that children should have an adult companion at home and in all activities to assure parental guidance and supervision. Children must receive attention and care to complete their home, school, and community responsibilities.

Table 2. Correlation Matrix for Family-Related and Management-Related Factors with the Elements of Change

	Knowledge	Attitude	Skill
Family Ties	.622**	.574**	.604**
Family Status	.404**	.685**	.561**
Family Responsibility	.672**	.620**	.603**
Parental Authority	.601**	.485**	.418**

Correlation Matrix for Management Related Factors to Elements of Change			
	Knowledge	Attitude	Skill
Policy Formulation	.585**	.440**	.468**
Policy Implementation	.590**	.446**	.412**
Decision Making	.307**	.188	.279**
Leadership Style	.689**	.735**	.836**

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

$\pm 0.01 - \pm 0.20$ Negligible Correlation (NC)

$\pm 0.21 - \pm 0.40$ Low Correlation (LC)

$\pm 0.41 - \pm 0.60$ Moderate Correlation (MC)

$\pm 0.61 - \pm 0.80$ High Correlation (HC)

$\pm 0.81 - \pm 0.99$ Very High Correlation (VHC)

± 1 Perfect Correlation (PC)

Management-related factors. The leadership style has very high correlations (VHC) with skill, $r(98) = .836, p < .001$ and has high correlations (HC) in both knowledge $r(98) = .689, p < .001$ and attitude $r(98) = .735, p < .001$. That leadership style encompasses political considerations such as governance awareness and comprehension of diverse policy designs and their roles and responsibilities, service delivery, policy and decision-making, resource discovery, and network creation. It also implies that the leadership style concerns political obligations, given that most responders are local public officials whom their people will scrutinize. As part of their job as managers, public officials in the area give strict orders to ensure their policies, programs, and projects get done. They said it is essential to improve management delivery because people need to know how the program helps them improve in many ways, such as their knowledge, attitude, and skills. The respondents also think it is vital to decide with their coworkers so they can deal with any problems. If they are willing to share findings with them and are ready for any issues or concerns, they may face, they are ready for any issues or concerns they may face, which means they are prepared for any problems or concerns they may face while in their post. People will get something out of their projects since other departments will be brought in to help with related tasks and serve the people. There are a lot of political issues and worries, which makes the political scene very intense. So, they need to improve their ability to deal with disagreements.

Conclusions

From the derive findings, the herein conclusion was drawn: On the Knowledge aspect, politically, the respondents had an impression that they were doing well with their political obligations. It shows that the leaders'

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knowledge regarding the discharge and execution of policies is highly favorable. This means that all aspects of dissemination, funding, professional consultation, and networking were included as part of the plan to realize the formulated policy. On the Attitude aspect, the local public official who filled out the survey thought that respect for oneself and others was one of the essential qualities of a leader. Respondents had generally shown a good relationship with other people. The interaction and community responsibility they demonstrated were positive and appropriate for people who assume offices in the government. On the Skill aspect, the local public official generally showed that they are competent in public service, leading the session, exchanging deliberation, and debate. It means that constituents had the best leader, and their vote was not put to waste. Name recall and popularity are some of the campaign strategies of our local public officials; very seldom that they present themselves as competent and qualified. Local public officials can consider aspects of decision-making to serve their constituents better. This also signals the leadership skills of the local public officials because decision-making requires stable and strong leadership qualities to weigh the information on hand before the final stage of decision-making. Respondents are strict in formulating and implementing the drafted policies they had. Leadership was assumed at the right time and the right juncture.

Recommendations

The local public officials, particularly at the City and Municipal levels like the Councilors and Barangay chairperson, must look into the management-related factors used in this study. Clarity of leadership and governance perspectives may also be understood by the public so that misinterpretation and negative impressions may be avoided. Public servants like barangay chairman are also managers on their political turf and cannot divest themselves of their responsibilities. Their planning must encompass multiple objectives, some of which may be conflicting or poorly defined in law. Electoral cycles and the brief tenure of many political executives make it difficult for career public managers to argue the salience of the most extended term proposed by President Duterte. Creation of Elements of Change Workshop (ECW), which include and is not limited to the value of service and commitment to work, and development activities must be offered to the leaders so that they will learn together to strengthen a set of changes needed particularly in the attitude aspect. They will, after that, be able to serve more and give confidence in themselves as competent. The local public officials should also be statesman-like in their manner of speech, attitude toward their constituents, and knowledge of several issues. This is possible by educating themselves during their private time or by attending the Elements of Change Workshop. Other researchers may replicate this study using variables to refute or confirm results and findings.

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